

The Effects of Applying Linguistic Principles and Teaching Techniques in Teaching English at Secondary School in Thailand

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Abstract—The ultimate purpose of this investigation was to determine the teachers' opinions as well as students' opinions towards the Adapted English Lessons. The subjects of the study were 5 Thai teachers, who teach English, and 85 Grade 10 mixed-ability students at Triamudom Suksa Pattanakarn Ratchada School, Bangkok, Thailand. The research instruments included questionnaires and the informal interview. The data from the research instruments was collected and analyzed concerning linguistic principles of minimal pair and articulatory phonetics as well as teaching techniques of mimicry-memorization; vocabulary substitution drills, language pattern drills, reading comprehension exercise, practicing listening, speaking and writing skill and communicative activities; informal talk and free writing. The data was statistically compiled according to an arithmetic percentage. The results showed that the teachers and students have very highly positive opinions towards adapting linguistic principles for teaching and learning phonological accuracy. Teaching techniques provided in the Adapted English Lessons can be used efficiently in the classroom. The teachers and students have positive opinions towards them too.

Keywords—Applying linguistic principles and teaching techniques, teachers' and students' opinions, teaching English, the Adapted English Lessons.

I. INTRODUCTION

FROM the researcher's earlier investigation about the problems in teaching English at Thai Secondary Schools, some teachers mentioned that their students have difficulties with English segmental phonemes and supra-segmental phonemes. Students cannot pronounce English phonemes such as /v//θ/ /ð//z//ʃ//t/ correctly. They have a problem with initial and final consonant cluster sounds for example /θr-//fr-//sk/ and /-ft/. They do not know when adding -ed in finite verbs the final sounds can be pronounced /-d//-t//-id//. Most students do not know which syllable should be stressed. Some of them do not use the pattern of intonation 233 for yes-no questions or 231 for Wh-questions. Consequently, they speak English with neither stress nor intonation. Moreover, English subject is taught as a foreign language and Thai language is used as a lingua franca in Thailand. Most Thai secondary students are usually just exposed to English in the classroom for about 4 periods a week. They have little opportunity to use or produce

English for communication. Their English communication ability is not high. To solve these problems, the Adapted English Lessons 1-3 were constructed. The theme of the lessons is based on language function of asking for and giving directions. Linguistic principles are applied for teaching consonant sounds and final cluster sounds. VDOs from YouTube are suggested to provide an opportunity for students to listen to sounds from native speakers of English. Furthermore, a variety of teaching techniques are used for the purpose of teaching language accuracy and fluency.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Linguistic Principles for Teaching English Phonological Accuracy

1) Minimal Pair

The main reason why minimal pair has been used in teaching pronunciation is that it can discriminate 2 phonemes. [1] This principle is used in the Adapted English Lessons for teaching a phoneme /θ/ which does not occur in the Thai consonant sound system, most of Thai students cannot distinguish when they pronounce *tree* and *three*. Then the words *mat* and *math* are used. The students were asked to pronounce these 2 final sounds repeatedly until they were aware of how /-t/ is different from /-θ/, as well as being able to pronounce these 2 phonemes correctly.

2) Articulatory Phonetics

Articulatory phonetics can assist students on how to pronounce consonant phonemes through 3 main principles; places of articulation, manners of articulation and voicing. [2] Besides practicing the final sound /θ/, the students have to practice the final cluster sounds of /-ft//-st/ as they are in the high frequency words used for asking for and giving directions, such as *left*, *east*, *west* etc. To describe the characteristic of these phonemes, articulatory phonetics is used. For instance, teachers can describe or demonstrate using tip of the tongue and alveolar for pronouncing /-t/ or place a tongue between upper lip and lower lip for pronouncing /-θ/. This linguistic principle is used for teaching the cluster sounds as well.

B. Combination of Language Accuracy and Language Fluency

Thai students spend 12 years studying English in primary and high school, however, their English proficiency is low.

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Thai teachers who teach English always complain that their students are quite poor in linguistic and communicative competency. To solve the problem, several principles from methods of language teaching are taken into account. Exercises or activities that can activate the students to achieve language accuracy prior to using it for communication will be designed in the Adapted English Lessons.

Practicing English pronunciation and practicing language accuracy repeatedly are from Audiolingual Method. [3]

Comprehension checking exercises after reading passage is from Noam Chomsky who believes that human beings learn language through thinking and understanding mentioned as Cognitive Learning Theory.[4]

Using language function as well as communicative activities is from Communicative Language Teaching Approach. Reference [5] mentions that Wilkins in 1976 considered about within a social context, language users need to perform certain functions.

III. METHODOLOGY

Since the samples of the study and the research instruments are already stated. Then details on the Adapted Lessons, Questionnaires and Procedures of the study are described.

A. The Adapted English Lessons

The Adapted English Lessons consist of three lessons. Details of each lesson are as follows:

Lesson one concentrates on pronunciation. Minimal pair of /-t/ and /-θ/, cluster sounds of /-ft/, /-st/, primary stress on the syllable in front of -ment and -tion are taught and practiced. This lesson also focuses on practicing a dialogue of asking for and giving directions through the teaching techniques of mimicry-memorization.

Lesson two focuses on listening and speaking. The students are asked to listen to a conversation from CD. After that they fill in the blanks to make a short conversation. Then they work in pairs and make three conversations with his/her friend by using the words provided. Finally, each pair chooses only one conversation to draw a simple map showing the directions of the place.

Lesson three emphasizes on pronunciation of /-t/, /-d/, /-id/ with past tense verbs that end with -ed. This lesson also focuses on checking reading comprehension. At the end of the lesson the students write a short essay about 8-10 sentences describing the directions from school to their house, and they draw a simple map for their essay.

B. Questionnaires Asking Teachers' and Students' Opinions towards the Adapted English Lessons

There are 2 questionnaires. One questionnaire is designed for the teachers and the other is for the students. They are constructed with items measured on a five point rating scale plus open-ended questions seeking descriptive data. The five point rating scales are Strongly agree, Agree, Moderate, Disagree and Strongly disagree.

C. Procedures of the Study

1. The research instruments were written and piloted with 1 English teacher.
2. The research instruments were improved according to the teacher's comments and suggestions concerning the format, concepts and wording.
3. Before experimenting 5 teachers discussed with the researcher on the purposes of the lesson, how to teach and checking the answer keys.
4. The Adapted English Lessons were experimented. It took 100 minutes to finish teaching each lesson.
5. The samples of the study were asked to complete the questionnaires.
6. Data from the questionnaires was analyzed.

IV. RESULTS OF THE STUDY

A. Teachers' Bio-data

Three female and two male teachers participated in this study. They are in the age range of 27-30. They finished their bachelor's degree majoring in English or teaching English. One of them is studying in master's degree program majoring in teaching English whereas the other three are studying in master's degree program majoring in educational linguistics.

B. Quantitative Data from Rating Scale Questions

TABLE I
TEACHERS' OPINIONS TOWARDS LINGUISTIC PRINCIPLES FOR TEACHING PHONOLOGICAL ACCURACY

	Strongly agree	Agree
1. Minimal pair of <i>mat</i> and <i>math</i> can help students to pronounce final sounds /-t/, /-θ/.	80%	20%
2. Practicing how to pronounce cluster sounds /-ft/, /-st/ is useful for students.	80%	20%
3. Practicing how to pronounce the stress on the syllable in front of the morphemes -tion, -ment is appropriate.	80%	20%
4. Practicing how to pronounce /-t/, /-d/, /-id/ for past tense verbs are appropriate.	80%	20%
5. Articulatory phonetics is useful for describing consonant sounds.	80%	20%

TABLE II
TEACHERS' OPINIONS TOWARDS TEACHING TECHNIQUE OF MIMICRY-MEMORIZATION

	Strongly agree	Agree	Moderate
1. Mimicry memorization activity for practicing pronunciation, vocabularies, sentences in dialogues is appropriate to your students' ability.	40%	40%	20%
2. Practicing in pairs after mimicry-memorization activity encourage your students to ask and answer in dialogues.	40%	40%	20%

TABLE III
TEACHERS' OPINIONS TOWARDS TEACHING TECHNIQUE FOR COMPREHENSION CHECK

	Strongly agree	Agree
1. There are sufficient vocabularies describing asking for and giving directions in the reading passage.	40%	60%
2. There are sufficient sentence structures describing asking for and giving directions in the reading passage.	40%	60%
3. Wh-questions after reading can check the students' understanding the reading passage.	40%	60%

TABLE IV
TEACHERS' OPINIONS TOWARDS TEACHING TECHNIQUES FOR TEACHING LISTENING SKILL

	Strongly agree	Agree
1. Practicing listening a dialogue from CD spoken by native speaker of English can assist your students gain listening skill.	80%	20%
2. Asking students to repeat after the dialogue can assist your students to pronounce in word and sentence level.	80%	20%
3. Asking students to fill word(s) or phrase that they hear from the dialogue in the blanks can stimulate your students to pay attention in listening.	80%	20%

TABLE V
TEACHERS' OPINIONS TOWARDS TEACHING TECHNIQUES FOR TEACHING VOCABULARY AND PREPOSITION

	Strongly agree	Agree
1. Reviewing how to spell vocabularies by asking students fill the letters in the blanks to construct words is suitable.	60%	40%
2. Reviewing vocabulary activity used in warm up stage is appropriate.	60%	40%
3. Using a picture and a map help your students understand the meaning of preposition.	80%	20%

TABLE VI
TEACHERS' OPINIONS TOWARDS TEACHING TECHNIQUES FOR TEACHING LANGUAGE FLUENCY

	Strongly agree	Agree
1. Pair work can stimulate your students to practice English listening and speaking in a dialogue.	40%	60%
2. Asking students to write 8-10 sentences describing the directions from school to their house is appropriate.	40%	60%
3. Asking students to draw a map describing the directions from school to their house is appropriate.	40%	60%

TABLE VII
TEACHERS' OPINIONS TOWARDS THE ADAPTED ENGLISH LESSONS

	Strongly agree	Agree
1. The Adapted English Lesson 1- Lesson 3 can assist your students gain confidence in asking for and giving directions.	40%	60%

C. Qualitative Data from Open-ended Questions

1) Teachers' Opinions towards Linguistic Principles in Teaching Phonological Accuracy

All 5 teachers mentioned that minimal pair and articulatory phonetics for teaching consonant sounds and teaching how to stress are excellent. They stated that using YouTube for teaching how to pronounce /-t/, /-d/, /-id/ and how to put stress on the syllable in front of the morphemes -tion,-mentis appropriate. Because the students prefer to listen to native speakers of English, who are good models for them to imitate how to stress and pronounce the English words correctly. The teachers also mentioned that the students are more aware of pronouncing /-t/, /-d/, /-id/when they see V₁+ ed.

2) Teachers' Opinions towards Language Function

All 5 teachers agreed that language function of asking for and giving directions can prepare the students use of English language for communication. One of these teachers said that exercises focusing on listening, speaking and writing including a final task of asking the students to draw a simple

map and then describe the route to their friends are good. This teacher revealed that these exercises can assist the students to use varieties of sentence for communication.

3) Teachers' Opinions towards Adapting Teaching Materials

One teacher mentioned that the Adapted English Lessons is appropriate for Thai students. He suggested that there should be a training course for Thai teachers to train how to adapt English supplementary materials. He stated the advantages of adapting materials by local teachers are it can solve the students' real problems and it can serve what the students really need.

4) Teachers' Opinions towards the Adapted English Lessons

One teacher mentioned that her students are more confident in speaking and writing about asking for and giving directions by the end of the experiment than she first met them. All 5 teachers were satisfied with the adapted lessons.

D. Students' Bio-data

There are 79 female and 6 male students in this experiment. They are in the age range of 15-16.

E. Quantitative Data from Rating Scale Questions

TABLE VIII
STUDENTS' OPINIONS TOWARDS LINGUISTIC PRINCIPLES FOR TEACHING PHONOLOGICAL ACCURACY

	Strongly agree	Agree	Moderate
1. Practicing how to pronounce final sounds /-t/, /-θ/ is useful.	45%	49%	6%
2. Practicing how to pronounce cluster sounds /-ft/, /-st/ is useful.	74%	22%	4%
3. Practicing how to pronounce stress on the syllable in front of morphemes -tion,-ment by using VDO from YouTube is useful.	49%	40%	11%
4. Practicing how to pronounce /-t/, /-d/, /-id/ for past tense verbs is appropriate.	50%	46%	4%

TABLE IX
STUDENTS' OPINIONS TOWARDS TEACHING TECHNIQUE OF MIMICRY-MEMORIZATION

	Strongly agree	Agree	Moderate	Disagree
1. Mimicry memorization activity for practicing pronunciation, vocabularies, sentences in dialogues is appropriate to your ability.	57%	337%	5%	1%
2. Practicing in pairs after Mimicry-Memorization activity encourage you to ask-answer in dialogues.	57%	38%	4%	1%

TABLE X
STUDENTS' OPINIONS TOWARDS TEACHING TECHNIQUE FOR COMPREHENSION CHECK

	Strongly agree	Agree	Moderate
1. Reading passage is appropriate for learning asking for and giving directions.	54%	39%	7%
2. Wh-questions after reading help you to understand the passage.	46%	39%	15%

TABLE XI
STUDENTS' OPINIONS TOWARDS TEACHING TECHNIQUES FOR TEACHING LISTENING SKILL

	Strongly agree	Agree	Moderate
1. Practicing listening a dialogue from CD spoken by native speaker of English can assist you gain listening skill.	44%	48%	8%
2. Asking you to fill word(s) or phrase that you hear from the dialogue in the blanks stimulate you to pay attention in listening.	39%	50%	11%

TABLE XII
STUDENTS' OPINIONS TOWARDS TEACHING TECHNIQUES FOR TEACHING VOCABULARY AND PREPOSITION

	Strongly agree	Agree	Moderate
1. Reviewing how to spell vocabularies by asking you fill the letters in the blanks to construct words is suitable.	45%	50%	5%
2. Reviewing vocabularies should be done before learning a lesson.	46%	44%	10%
3. Using a picture and a map help you understand the meaning of preposition.	51%	39%	10%

TABLE XIII
STUDENTS' OPINIONS TOWARDS TEACHING TECHNIQUES FOR TEACHING LANGUAGE FLUENCY

	Strongly agree	Agree	Moderate
1. Pair work can stimulate you to practice speaking.	48%	46%	6%
2. Pair work can stimulate you to ask for and give directions with your friend.	47%	52%	1%
3. Asking you to write 8-10 sentences describing the directions from school to you house is appropriate.	48%	35%	17%
4. Asking you to draw a map describing the directions from school to your house is appropriate.	49%	38%	13%

TABLE XIV
STUDENTS' OPINIONS TOWARDS THE ADAPTED ENGLISH LESSONS

	Strongly agree	Agree	Moderate
1. The Adapted English Lesson 1- Lesson 3 can assist you gain confidence in asking for and giving directions.	48%	39%	13%

F. Qualitative Data from Open-ended Questions

Some students expressed their opinions as follows:

- Lesson 1 is very useful for me because I can pronounce English sounds better and correctly.
- I know more on how to pronounce English sounds.
- It is good because I have an opportunity to practice pronunciation.
- It is very difficult for me to pronounce /θ/, but I can practice it with a teacher.
- Listening to native speakers of English from YouTube is good. I would like to listen more.
- The theme of asking for and giving directions is essential for everyday life. Lessons are understandable.
- I learn more vocabularies.
- The lessons are easy to understand and I can use the vocabularies and sentences in my everyday life.

V. DISCUSSION

A. The Effects of Applying Linguistic Principles in Teaching Phonological Accuracy

In the researcher's opinion, there are three main factors that the Adapted English Lessons can help the teachers teach pronunciation effectively. Firstly, minimal pair can definitely distinguish 2 phonemes of /-t/ /-θ/ as well as articulatory phonetics can help the teachers explain how to pronounce phonemes physically in terms of places of articulation, manners of articulation and voicing. The second factor is the teachers' educational background as mentioned in the teachers' Bio-data earlier. So each teacher can be a good model of pronouncing all phonemes focused in the Adapted English Lessons. Most of the students were satisfied with practicing English pronunciation. Some of them stated that they wanted to practice more with these 5 teachers. The last factor is learning how to pronounce English sounds can serve the students' needs. Normally, Thai students are asked to learn and practice on grammatical knowledge in morphology and syntax rather than phonology in their usual English class. [6]

B. The Effects of Applying Teaching Techniques in the Adapted English Lessons

There are 4 reasons why teaching techniques adapted in the Adapted English Lessons can be used effectively as discussed below.

1) Language Function

The language function of asking for and giving directions in English is necessary for Thai students. This language function is always used in the students' real life. For each year there are a large amount of tourists who come to visit Thailand. Generally, they use English for communication and they always ask Thais how to get to somewhere. Then the language function of asking for and giving directions applied in the Adapted English Lessons are useful and relevant to Thai students' everyday life. Reference [7] states that the importance of the language functions is they can be used for communication purpose.

2) Concept of Accuracy and Fluency

One of the main problems in teaching English in Thailand is Thai teachers see a high level of problems resulting from students' insufficient background of the language and lack of exposure to English. [8] From the statement, it can be pointed out that Thai students need to practice both language accuracy and language fluency. The main purpose of the Adapted English Lessons is leading the students to gain sufficient language accuracy i.e. they can pronounce and stress sounds correctly and confidently, at the same time they have adequate vocabularies and sentence structures for use in informal talk and free writing task. It is now very clear that fluency and accuracy are both important goals to pursue in communicative language teaching. There are strong theoretical reasons for claiming that focus on form is not just facilitative of learning but may even be necessary. [9] It is also stated in reference [10] that students learning fluency without accuracy is one of

the problems in language teaching and learning. Pidgin language as an error might be occurred. Fluency and accuracy are two factors which determine the success of the students, who can communicate fluently with language accuracy.

3) The Multi-Syllabus

Reference [11] defines 'multi-syllabus' as the syllabus that shows a combination of items from grammar, lexis, language function, situations, topics, tasks, different language skills or pronunciation issues. The Adapted English Lessons can be considered as a multi-syllabus due to its components of pronunciation, vocabulary, sentence structures, language skills, language function and task-based activities. Harmer also states that as the process of learning goes on by the multi-syllabus, the grammar syllabus will have to change to accommodate some of the other claims; the list of functions will shift around to accommodate the grammar, and the tasks will have to take account of the language at the students' disposal for the performing of the tasks. In this case the students get the most benefit from practicing varieties of components provided in the Adapted English Lessons.

4) Using Native Speakers of English Sounds from CD and YouTube

From the data gained the teachers are highly satisfied with techniques of using CD and YouTube. Many students revealed that they preferred listening to native speakers of English. They wanted to listen more. An advantage of using YouTube is the students can see the movement of the speech articulations and hear the sound(s) at the same time. It can activate them in practicing phonological accuracy. Reference [12] reveals that digital media can be used to assist students in mastering grammar, vocabulary and also pronunciation.

5) Teachers' and Students' Opinions towards the Adapted English Lessons

The teachers and students are satisfied with the Adapted English Lesson 1-3. The teachers think that the Adapted Lessons can help their students to gain the language knowledge and the opportunities to speak and write on the language function of asking for and giving directions. The students say that they prefer learning pronunciation and exercises or activities provided. They like working in pairs. They also mention that practicing in pair work after mimicry-memorization activity encourages them to ask and answer in dialogues. They gain more confidence for writing a short essay describing the directions from school to their home.

C. The Need of Constructing Supplementary Materials for Local Use

Reference [13] mentions that the problem involved textbooks used in the countries of teaching English as a foreign language is whether they are appropriate for local context or not. Using supplementary materials is one of the choices to solve this problem. The main reason, why the Adapted Lessons can be as the useful supplementary materials at Triamudom Suksa Pattanakarn Ratchada School is that they can serve the students' needs and lacks. That is the students

want to practice English that can be used for their everyday life or can solve their problems of pronunciation such as word stress or pronounce final sounds with past verbs adding -ed. Reference [14] says that recently he has been involved in many projects to develop local materials in many countries. He clarifies that the demands of materials for local use are from teachers, as material writers, want to design materials that can meet the generalized needs and wants of actual students who are learning English in a specific environment with specific objectives.

D. Problems Occurred and the Solution

The researcher noticed that teachers spent time explaining what they are good at. Two teachers took about 130 minutes instead of 100 minutes to finish teaching the Adapted Lesson 1. They used 75 minutes for teaching pronunciation; they had only 25 minutes left for teaching mimicry-memorization activity. To solve the problem there was a discussion among 5 teachers and the researcher. It was discovered that two teachers who could not finish teaching Lesson 1 in time because it was their first time of teaching these groups of students. They explained in more details on how to pronounce sounds. They agreed that they have to manage time better next lessons. Another problem is three teachers worried at the reading comprehension. They mentioned that the students copied the answers in the phrase level from the reading passage. They wanted them to write the answers in full sentences using the students' own words. This is one of the misunderstanding teaching concepts. To solve this problem the researcher asked these teachers whether the students should answer wh-questions in full sentences or not. From the discussion all teachers finally agreed that finding out the answers shows the students' comprehension, and it means that the students understand the reading passage. Then it is not necessary to ask them to answer in full sentences. Furthermore, three teachers complained that the students wanted them to teach article and preposition of place even though they had already studied these 2 grammar points. The students also forgot vocabularies and expressions of giving directions when they were asked to describe the way from school to their house. To solve the problem all teachers agreed to use 3 strategies. The first strategy is the teachers should be an assistant who walk around the classroom to help when the students forget the grammar points, vocabularies or expressions. The second strategy is whenever the students get the wrong answers the teacher immediately corrects and explains the correct grammars. The third strategy is asking the less-able students to work in pairs with the more-able students who can assist the less-able ones when they have the difficulties with grammar points.

VI. RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Thai teachers who teach English should take notice about what their students' lacks and needs are. In this case they know the students' real problems of learning English in their school.

2. Then the teachers should be trained on adapting the efficient local materials used in their school. The idea of constructing local supplement materials should be encouraged by the Ministry of Education in Thailand.

APPENDIX

The Adapted English Lessons

Lesson 1

Asking For and Giving Directions

(Pronunciation and dialogues)

Time 100 minutes

Warm up activity

1. Look at the pictures below. Guess what they are.
2. Look at the following pictures. Write the correct letters to make the words.

[15]

1. _ r _ _ f _ _ l _ _ h _ _

[16]

2. _ n _ _ r _ _ c _ _ o _ _

[17]

3. T- _ _ n _ _ i _ _

[18]

4. s _ _ n _ _ s _ _

3. Look at the signs. What do they mean?

1. t _ _ n l _ _ t

2. _ _ r _ _ r _ _ h _ _

4. Write the correct meaning.

N stands for _ _ _ _ _

S stands for _ _ _ _ _

W stands for _ _ _ _ _

E stands for _ _ _ _ _

Review preposition

1. Match the preposition with the pictures.
 behind between in next to under
 in front of in the middle on
 opposite on the left on the right

[19]

2. Look at the map.
 Work in pairs within 10 minutes and write the suitable preposition in the blanks.

- The music store is _____ Santos Dumont Street and Rosa e Silva Avenue.
- The hospital is _____ the pet shop.
- The toy store is _____ the music store and the restaurant.
- The supermarket is _____ the restaurant.
- The fast food restaurant is _____ Amélia Street.
- The bookstore is _____ the supermarket.
- The bank is on Santos Dumont Street _____ the flower shop.
- The School is _____ Amélia Street and Rosa e Silva Avenue.
- The pet shop is _____ Amélia Street.
- The flower shop is _____ Santos Dumont Street

3. Check the answers together.

Warm up activity

Minimal pair: /-t/ /-th/

1. Look at the pictures. What are they?

[21]

It is a m ____.

[22]

It is about m __ t __.

2. Practice how to pronounce /t/ /th/ with your teacher.
 And practice more from VDO clip. [23]

Cluster sounds: /-ft/ /-st/

1. Look at the picture. What is it?

[24]

It is a g __ f __.

2. Listen to your teacher and repeat the words with /-ft/.
 lift left raft soft craft

3. Work in pairs, think of words that end with *ft* and pronounce them.

4. Look at the picture. What is it?

[25]

It is a c __ s __.

5. Listen to your teacher and repeat the words with /-st/.
 best fast last lost must trust

6. Work in pairs, think of words that end with *st* and pronounce them.

Stress:

Primary stress on the syllable in front of *-tion*, *-ment*

1. Look at the following words.

act, state, depart, treat

If you want to make them into nouns, you can add *-tion* and *-ment*.

Act → action, state → station depart → department
 treat → treatment

2. Listen to your teacher on how to stress the words that end with *-tion* and *-ment* and repeat after him/her.

3. Practice how to stress the words that end with *-tion* and *-ment* from the websites. [26]

Dialogues and practice

Warm up activity

Instructions: Look at the picture of Dialogue 1 and answer the questions.

Who is the man?

Who is the girl? What is the man looking for?

Mimicry-memorization activity

Instructions: Repeat sentences in the dialogue after the teacher.
 Memorize the dialogue.

Dialogue 1

A tourist: Excuse me. Can you tell me where the nearest **1.MRT station** is?

A student: Certainly, it's not far. Walk **2.north** for 200 metres and you will see the **3.traffic lights**.

A tourist: I'll see the traffic lights.

A student: Then turn left. You'll see the **4. MRT station** on your right side **5.opposite** the cinema.

A tourist: Thank you.

A student: You're welcome.

Dialogue 2

A tourist: Excuse me. Can you tell me where the nearest **1.department store** is?

A student: Certainly, it's not far. Walk **2. south** for 200 metres and you will see the **3.intersection**.

A tourist: I'll see the intersection.

A student: Then turn left. You'll see the **4. department Store** on your right side **5.next to** the cinema.

A tourist: Thank you.

A student: You're welcome.

Now work in pairs and practice Dialogue 3 – Dialogue 5 by using the provided words.

Dialogue 3

1.bank 2. east 3. signpost 4. bank 5. in front of

Dialogue 4

1.police station 2. west 3. T-junction 4.police station 5.behind

Dialogue 5

1. railway station 2. north 3. signpost 4. railway station
5. beside

Production Activity

Instructions: Work in pairs. Make your dialogue and present in front of the class.

Lesson 2

Asking For and Giving Directions

(Listening, speaking and writing)

Time 100 minutes

Warm up activity

1. Review the students' existing knowledge about asking for and giving directions by watching the VDO clip. [27]

2. Divide students into small groups of 5-6. Ask them to write down words related "directions and location" for 10 minutes. The group who can get the most words will be the winner.

Listening 1

1. Listen to a conversation. [28]

Winnie: Excuse me. Is there a post office near here?

Man: Yes, there's a post office on Third Avenue.

Winnie: Great! How do I get there?

Man: You can walk. It's easy! Go straight ahead, and turn left onto Main Street.

Winnie: Thanks.

Man: Then turn right at the bus station and go past the bank.

Winnie: Er... OK. So it's past the bank.

Man: Then turn left onto Park Road.

Winnie: Left onto Park Road. I see.

Man: Yeah. Keep going and the post office is on the right, next to a large supermarket.

Winnie: Hmm. Thanks a lot.

Man: You're welcome.

Winnie: Taxi!

2. Listen and practice. Your teacher will pause sentence by sentence.

3. Read aloud together.

4. Ask your teacher if you do not understand anything in the conversation or you can ask how to pronounce the words.

Listening 2

Instructions: 1. Listen and complete the conversation. [28]

A: Excuse me. Is there a 1 _____ near here?

B: Yes, there is. It's on 2 _____

A: Great. How do I get there?

B: Turn right at the bank and go straight ahead. It's 3 _____

A: Thanks. Oh, and is there a 4 _____?

B: Yes. It's 5 _____ the supermarket.

A: Thanks a lot!

2. Draw a simple map for the conversation 2.

3. Work in pairs. Use the words to make more conversations and practice with your friend.

Conversation one: 1. bookstore 2. Fifth Avenue 3. on the right
4. florist 5. across from

Conversation two: 1. stationery store 2. Main Street 3. on the corner
4. music store 5. behind

Conversation three: 1. drugstore 2. Park road 3.near the hotel
4. shoe store 5. in front of

4. In your pair choose one conversation from Conversation one–
Conversation three and draw a simple map.

Writing/ Speaking

1. Work in pairs and think of a place that is not far and you can describe how to get to in 5-8 sentences. Draw a simple map, but do not mark the route.

2. Give your map to your friend and describe your route.

3. Ask your friend and check whether your friend can draw the correct route on your map or not. If your friend cannot draw the route correctly, describe your route again.

Lesson 3

Asking For and Giving Directions

(Pronunciation, Reading and Writing)

Time 100 minutes

Instructions:

1. Watch VDO Clips and practice /-t/ /-d/ /-id/ with past tense verbs that end with -ed. [29]
If you do not understand anything on YouTube, ask your teacher to explain more.
2. Find the words that have -ed. in the following reading passage and write on the blackboard.
3. Pronounce the words. If anyone pronounces incorrectly, correct their pronunciation together.

Reading

Instructions: Read the following passage aloud. [30]

Underline the words that you do not understand. Then ask your teacher the meaning of those words.

Kim called at Tom's house to tell him how to go to a holiday bungalow at Pine Bay. Tom was not in, and so Kim left the following note.

Dear Tom,

I am sorry I called when you were out. This is how to reach the bungalow on your motorbike. Drive out of Steeltown long Factory Road and watch for a major intersection with traffic lights after about 5 km. The left turn is marked with a sign to Charlton. When you have made this turn, you will be on route 3, which leads directly to Pine Bay. You should then drive for about 130 km and pass through Charlton and Middleton before looking for the Pine Bay signpost.

On the last section of the road before Pine Bay, you will see a large school on the right hand side and you will find a right hand turn soon after this building. There are other turns off the main road but this is the quickest and most direct way. Drive down this small road as far as you can until you can see the sea directly in front of you. Then turn left. (In fact you have no choice because the road goes nowhere else.)

You then pass through the small village of Pine View, and after the village you must look again for a right turn. This turn is marked by a sign which reads "Rock Cottages". You should continue along it for about a kilometer before it divides. Take the left branch for about ½ km and you will find the bungalow near the end of the track on the left. It is far away from other bungalows and is painted red, so there is no possibility of confusion.

I am looking forward to seeing you there around five o'clock on Friday afternoon.

Kim

Instructions: Work in pairs and answer the questions.

1. What two things indicate the left turn off Factory Road?
2. What two things will help Tom to know when he must turn off route 3?
3. Why is it best for Tom to take the turn immediately after the school?
4. Why must Tom turn left when he reaches the sea?

5. When should Tom start looking for the "Rock Cottages" signpost?
6. Approximately how far is it from Pine View village to the bungalow?
7. What two things will help Tom identify the bungalow?

Grammar Focus

"a" in front of *holiday*.

"the" in front of *bungalow*.

Not "a" and "the" in front of *Pine Bay*.

"a" is used when something is mentioned for the first time and is unknown.

"the" is used when there is only one example of something or when the thing is well-known and when something is mentioned again.

Names of people, streets and towns do not have "a" or "the".

Practice

Exercise 1

Instructions: Fill the blanks with *a, the* or nothing. [30]

When _____ Gimin drove into _____ Medan, he immediately began to look for _____ petrol station. He was unable to find one and so he asked at _____ restaurant. _____ owner of _____ restaurant told him to drive down New Road until he reached _____ junction with Old Road. _____ Gimin turned to the left at _____ left at _____ crossroads and saw _____ petrol station 200 metres away. At that moment _____ car stopped. There was no petrol left in _____ tank. Gimin noticed that he had stopped outside _____ coffee bar and so he decided to have _____ cup of coffee before he pushed _____ car for _____ last 200metres.

Exercise 2

1. Find the words that have-ed. in Exercise 1 and write down.

2. Pronounce the words. If anyone pronounces incorrectly, correct their pronunciation.

3. Check your pronunciation with your teacher.

Exercise 3

Instructions: Choose a suitable preposition from the box to fill in the blanks. [30]

at, in, into, to, off, out of, under, down

1. The boys are playing _____ the yard.
2. Look at all those small boats _____ the harbour.
3. Mr. Lee used to live _____ Singapore, but he has recently moved _____ Bangkok. He lives _____ 304 Krung Kasem Road.
4. Miss Wiguna usually shops _____ Robinson's Supermarket
5. Please take all your books _____ the table and put them _____ this drawer.
6. The explorer set off _____ the South Pole.
7. Kim always sits _____ the back of the class, never _____ the middle.
8. He put the money on the table before he went _____ the room.
9. Several small children were playing _____ the street when I arrived _____ Mr. Hassan's house.

10. He ran _____ the hill and found his football _____ a car.

Exercise 4

Instructions: Reorder the words to make sentences. [30]

1. you, Go, way, until, this, station, the, gas, see

2. Take, fifth, lift, the, floor, the, to

3. blocks, minutes, right, then, Walk, and, 10, turn, for, then, walk, two, for

4. at, 145, street, the, the, for, Bus, wait, bus, Cross, stop, and

5. get, Store, 365, Department, Bus, off, and, at, Take, Central

6. lights, Wait, green, light, changes, the, traffic, the, until, at, to

7. you, left, Go, building, bridge, then, on, look, for, tall, under, and, the, a

8. get, and, you'll, intersection, the, the, station, see, When, subway, the, you, road, to, cross

Instructions: Write 8 -10 sentences that give directions to your friends to reach your house from school. Draw a simple map to help them to find your house easily.

To get to my house, _____

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REFERENCES

- [1] Spratt Mary, Pulverness Alan and Williams Melanie, *The Teaching Knowledge Test*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2005, p.15.
- [2] Fromkin Victoria, Rodman Robert and Hyams Nina, *An Introduction to Language*. (7thed). Boston: Thomson Higher Education, 2003, pp. 242-250.
- [3] Richards C. Jack and Rodgers S. Theodore, *Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching*. New York: Cambridge University Press, 1986, ch. 4.
- [4] Nunan David, Methodology. In *Practical English Language Teaching* (3rded.), Nunan David Ed. New York: McGraw-Hill, 2003, pp. 3-22.
- [5] Larsen-Freeman Diane and Anderson Marti, *Techniques & Principles in Language Teaching*. New York: Oxford University Press, 2011, p.115.

- [6] Sripicam Pasphong, Teaching English Grammar. In *Leaw Lung Lae Na (Thai words) English Teaching*, Wiriyaichitra Arunee Ed. Bangkok: Asia Press, 2012, pp.70-71.
- [7] Savignon J. Sandra, Interpreting Communicative Language Teaching. In *Communicative Language Teaching: Linguistic Theory and Classroom Practice*. Savignon Sandra J. Ed. London: Yale University Press, 2002, pp. 1-28.
- [8] Noom-ura Sripatham, English Teaching Problems in Thailand and Thai Teachers' Professional Development Needs. (Online Journal) *English Language Teaching*, vol. 6, no. 11, Oct. 2013, pp. 139-147.
- [9] Ellis Rod and Shintani Natsuko, *Exploring Language Pedagogy through Second Language Acquisition Research*. Oxon: Routledge, 2014, pp.15-18.
- [10] *Balancing Fluency and Accuracy*. in www.english-for-students.com/fluency-and-accuracy.html. (accessed 23 February 2015).
- [11] Harmer Jeremy, *The Practice of English Language Teaching*. (3rded.), Essex: Pearson Education. 2001, p.300.
- [12] Ware Paige, Liaw Meei-Ling and Warschauer Mark, The Use of Digital Media in Teaching English as an International Language. in *Principles and Practices for Teaching English as an International Language*, Lubna Alsagoff, Sandra Lee McKay, Guangwei Hu and Willy A. Renandya, Eds. New York: Edwards Brothers, 2012, pp. 67-84.
- [13] Matsuda Aya, Teaching Materials in EIL. in *Principles and Practices for Teaching English as an International Language*, Lubna Alsagoff, Sandra Lee McKay, Guangwei Hu and Willy A. Renandya, Eds. New York: Edwards Brothers, 2012, pp.168-185.
- [14] Tomlinson Brain, Materials Development. In *Pedagogy and Practice in Second Language Teaching*, Burns Anne and Richards Jack C, Eds. New York: Cambridge University Press, 2012, pp. 269-278.
- [15] <http://leds-news.blogspot.com/2014/01/use-leds-to-show-when-traffic-light-is.html>, (accessed 23 February 2015).
- [16] <http://urna.projects.unoc.net/media/traffic-intersection.png>, (accessed 23 February 2015).
- [17] <http://www.cambridgedrivingschool.net/how-to-deal-with-junctions.html>, (accessed 23 February 2015).
- [18] http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:Botanic_gardens_belfast_sign_post, (accessed 23 February 2015).
- [19] Oxenden Clive, Latham-Koenig Christina and Seligson Paul, *New English File*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1997, p.9.
- [20] <http://www.english-exercises.org/makeagame/viewgame.asp?id=17>, (accessed 25 February 2015).
- [21] http://www.google.co.th/search?q=mat&rlz=1T4AURU_enTH497TH497&tbm=isch&prmd=ivnsz&ei=nQo9U6yjMIWqrAe3k4CwBQ&start=60&sa=N, (accessed 25 February 2015).
- [22] <http://www.pragmaticmom.com/2013/01/2nd-grade-math-facts/>, (accessed 25 February 2015).
- [23] <http://www.slideshare.net/garcia58/pronun-t-vs-th>, <http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MKtZH0bN0W0>, (accessed 25 February 2015).
- [24] <http://www.horolive.com/astrology-hot/content04-10-2555-2.html#U8SY5tySw0M>, (accessed 25 February 2015).
- [25] <http://www.bloggang.com/viewdiary.php?id=coffeebake&month=09-2010&date=27&group=9&gblog=13>, (accessed 25 February 2015).
- [26] http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WcTFjYSRq_k, <http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=X1Rxb-78uZA>, (accessed 25 February 2015).
- [27] <http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=DA42nsvtsM>, (accessed 27 February 2015).
- [28] Craven Miles, *Breakthrough Plus Student Book 1*, Oxford: Macmillan Education. 2013, p.30.
- [29] <http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QfDH5BM02lo>, <http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2tYErI17g-U>, (accessed 27 February 2015).
- [30] Heaton B. Clark D.F, *Communication Target Book One*. Singapore: Longman. 1980, pp. 37-38, 40.